
The Fabricated Past: Harappan Civilization, Colonial Ideology, and Nationalism, A Pseudo- Archaeological Reconstruction of the Past of India

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ABSTRACT

This paper rigorously examines the trajectory of pseudo-archaeology in India, tracing its lineage from colonial constructs to its institutional entrenchment in nationalist agendas. Initially shaped by British archaeologists such as John Marshall and Mortimer Wheeler, Indian archaeology was heavily influenced by Eurocentric frameworks that interwove mythology into historical analysis. These colonial misinterpretations laid the groundwork for subsequent nationalist appropriations, particularly within the Hindutva movement, which sought to reimagine the Harappan Civilization as conterminous with Vedic culture and the Saraswati River. Post-independence, pseudo-archaeology evolved into a potent political instrument, employed to justify ethno-nationalist narratives while distorting historical inquiry. The rise of digital platforms and state-backed initiatives, including the Saraswati Heritage Project, further legitimized these narratives, reinforcing Vedic and Aryan claims on India's antiquity. This study elucidates the perils of pseudo-archaeology in shaping public discourse, enabling exclusionary ideologies, and undermining scientific rigor. By examining its colonial roots and modern revival, this paper underscores the critical need for evidence-based archaeological scholarship to counter politicized distortions of history and to preserve broader

historical awareness.

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Introduction:

The paper explores the critical interplay between archaeology, colonial ideology, and nationalism in the reinterpretation of India's ancient past, with particular attention to the Harappan Civilization. It underscores the persistent influence of pseudo-archaeological narratives—interpretations that deviate from empirical scientific methods to align with myths, speculative theories, and political ideologies. Originating during the colonial era, these narratives were shaped by figures like John Marshall and Mortimer Wheeler, who incorporated elements of mythology and speculative reasoning into their archaeological interpretations. Over time, this approach provided fertile ground for nationalist ideologies, particularly Hindutva, to redefine the Harappan Civilization as a precursor to Vedic culture and the mythical Saraswati River.

Pseudo-archaeology is characterized by its rejection of scientific rigor and reliance on mythological or anecdotal evidence. In the Indian context, this approach often seeks to validate epics like the *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* through archaeological endeavors. While colonial-era scholars introduced theories like the Aryan Invasion and used mythology to frame the decline of the Harappan Civilization, modern pseudo-archaeologists have extended these narratives to claim indigenous Vedic origins for the civilization. The influence of such ideologies is evident in the penetration of pseudo-archaeological methods into academic and governmental institutions, including the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) and leading universities.

The article critically examines the roots of these narratives, beginning with the colonial period when British archaeologists like Alexander Cunningham and Max Müller used archaeology to validate imperial ideologies. The discovery of the Harappan Civilization during John Marshall's tenure marked a turning point, as his interpretations heavily relied on historical analogies with Hindu mythology, associating Harappan artifacts with Shaivism and the mother goddess cult. Although these interpretations lacked scientific validation, they laid the groundwork for later nationalist reinterpretations.

Post-independence, the rise of the Aryan Invasion Theory under Mortimer Wheeler perpetuated this trend, further integrating Rigvedic mythology into archaeological discourse. The nationalist reimagining of the Harappan Civilization gained momentum with the rise of right-wing ideologies in India, particularly in 90s after the emergence of Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) and Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP). Scholars aligned with Hindutva ideologies have rebranded the Harappan Civilization as the Vedic Civilization, advancing claims that align with cultural and political agendas. These narratives, supported by speculative interpretations and selective readings of evidence, have sought to link the civilization with the mythical Saraswati River and extend its dating back to 7000 BCE.

The consequences of pseudo-archaeology in India are far-reaching, shaping public opinion through media and academic platforms while promoting exclusionary narratives that undermine the multicultural heritage of the subcontinent. By intertwining mythology with archaeology, these narratives risk eroding scientific rigor and distorting historical understanding. This article provides a critical analysis of these trends, emphasizing the need for a more evidence-based approach to archaeology to preserve the integrity of India's rich and diverse past.

Pseudo-archaeology and Cultural Distortions: A Critical Examination of Unscientific Practices:

Pseudo-archaeology, frequently termed "fringe archaeology," "fantastic archaeology," or "cult archaeology," represents a pervasive and controversial phenomenon that undermines the scientific foundations of archaeology. Unlike academic archaeology, which rigorously employs empirical methods and critical analysis, pseudo-archaeology thrives on speculative theories, misinterpretation of evidence, and sensationalism. These interpretations often reject established scientific principles in favor of narratives rooted in myths, pseudoscience, and cultural fantasies. A recurring theme within pseudo-archaeological discourse is the proposition that extraterrestrial beings played a decisive role in shaping early human civilizations—a notion sensationalized by Erich von Däniken in his influential yet debunked 1968 publication '*Chariots of the Gods*'. Others champion the existence of mythical advanced human civilizations, such as Atlantis or those described in ancient Indian epics like the Ramayana and Mahabharata. Such perspectives, popularized by figures like Graham Hancock in works such as *Fingerprints of the Gods* (1995), have captured the public imagination despite lacking credible evidence or scholarly support.

The nomenclature used to describe pseudo-archaeology reflects its contentious status within academic discourse. During the 1980s, John R. Cole (1980) and William H. Stiebing Jr. (1987) referred to these

practices as "cult archaeology," a term emphasizing their deviation from academic rigor. In the early 2000s, some scholars, including Tim Sebastian (2001), Robert J. Wallis (2003), Cornelius Holtorf (2006), and Gabriel Moshenska (2008), began using the term "elective paleontology," suggesting a more neutral or lenient characterization. However, this terminology was criticized by Garrett F. Fagan and Kenneth L. Feder (2006) for its apparent attempt to soften the serious implications of pseudo-archaeology, which they argued warrants a more accurate and assertive label. They advocated for the term "pseudo-archaeology," aligning with prominent archaeologists like Colin Renfrew (2006), who emphasized the need to confront such misrepresentations with intellectual rigor.

While pseudo-archaeology might be dismissed as harmless entertainment or alternative storytelling, its implications are far from benign. As Glyn Daniel remarked in 1977, such practices can be aptly described as "bullshit archaeology," a candid reflection of their departure from scholarly integrity. William H. Stiebing Jr. further noted that the frustration and disdain these practices evoke among professional archaeologists often remain confined to private discussions, as the language required to fully critique them is deemed inappropriate for formal discourse. This article explores the origins, methods, and implications of pseudo-archaeology, scrutinizing its role in perpetuating misinformation, fostering cultural appropriation, and undermining the credibility of legitimate archaeological inquiry.

Pseudo-archaeology in Indian Archaeological Practices and Institutional Impact:

Pseudo-archaeology is characterized by a set of core traits that are commonly employed by pseudoarchaeologists in India and globally. William H. Stiebing Jr. (1987) identifies three fundamental attributes of pseudo-archaeological theories: first, their unscientific methodologies and reliance on dubious evidence; second, their tendency to offer overly simplistic explanations to complex historical questions; and third, their portrayal of themselves as persecuted by the academic establishment, coupled with an ambivalent attitude toward the scientific principles of the Enlightenment.

In the Indian context, pseudoarchaeologists often prioritize mythological and anecdotal evidence over rigorous archaeological data. Their work frequently focuses on proving the historicity of epics and myths through various excavations and projects. Print and social media serve as primary platforms for disseminating their unscientific findings, often bypassing the peer-review process, although they have established their own journals to lend credibility to their claims. Alarming, their influence has penetrated major Indian institutions and organizations, including the Archaeological Survey of India,

state archaeological departments, and prominent universities such as Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Deccan College, Delhi University, and Allahabad University.

The origins of pseudo-archaeology in India are intertwined with the early development of archaeology during the British colonial period. British archaeologists and historians such as William Jones and Max Müller significantly contributed to its foundation, promoting theories like the Aryan Invasion or Migration. Similarly, Alexander Cunningham, while utilizing Buddhist texts for his research, often relied on mythology and folklore. Nonetheless, many of the sites excavated or surveyed by Cunningham were historically authenticated through inscriptions, coins, and other material evidence.

The discovery of the Harappan Civilization (Indus Valley Civilization) marked a pivotal moment in the history of pseudo-archaeology in India. Under the directorship of John Marshall, colonial archaeologists often prioritized antiquities over stratified excavation principles (Malik 1979: 188). Challenges such as the undeciphered Harappan script and its absence in ancient Indian literature fueled speculative interpretations. Consequently, Marshall and his colleagues resorted to interpreting Harappan artifacts through the lens of Early Historic Religion or Modern Hindu Religion and Society. Marshall's reports on the Indus Civilization explicitly linked Harappan artifacts to Shaivism, the mother goddess cult, and other elements of Hindu mythology, an approach mirrored in the works of his contemporaries, including D.R. Sahni, R. Banerji, and M.S. Vats. However, recent scholarship (Wright 2010; Clark 2007) demonstrates that many of these associations lack scientific credibility, revealing that Marshall's methodology facilitated the integration of folk tales, legends, and mythology into Indian archaeology, ultimately enabling right-wing narratives.

Following Marshall, Mortimer Wheeler, another influential figure, served as Director General of the Archaeological Survey of India and is credited as the "father of modern archaeology in India." However, Wheeler's reliance on Rigvedic mythology to explain the decline of the Indus Valley Civilization positioned him as a pivotal figure in the development of pseudoarchaeology. His Aryan Invasion Theory—later supported by his Indian protégés, including A. Ghosh, Krishna Deva, V.S. Aggarwal, B.B. Lal, A.H. Dani, F. Khan, and B.K. Thapar—blamed the Aryans for the fall of the Indus Civilization, further entrenching pseudo-archaeological interpretations in Indian discourse.

The trajectory of pseudo-archaeology in India post-independence can be divided into three distinct phases. The first phase (1947–1980) was marked by the dominance of Wheeler's Aryan Invasion Theory, which guided numerous excavations, including those linked to the Harappan Civilization and

the newly discovered Painted Gray Ware (PGW) culture. These efforts sought to establish Aryan presence in India's ancient past. The second phase replaced the Aryan Invasion Theory with the Aryan Migration Theory and saw the Archaeological Survey of India focus on substantiating the historicity of the *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata*. This period witnessed significant collaboration between archaeologists and university scholars, embedding cultural and ideological narratives within archaeological practices.

The third phase began with the rise of the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) and Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP). Following the BJP's ascension to power in 1999, Hindutva ideologies permeated Indian institutions, including archaeological research. Right-wing historians and archaeologists began advocating that the Harappan Civilization was the Vedic Civilization and that figures from the *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* were historical entities. Rejecting the Aryan Invasion and Migration theories, these scholars proposed an indigenous origin for the Harappan Civilization, aligning it with Vedic traditions to bolster a nationalist agenda.

Harappan Civilization, Rigveda, Colonial Ideology, and Hindutva:

Apart from Mesopotamia and Egypt, the Harappan civilization is one of the three major cradles of early civilizations in the Ancient East (*Childe 1950*). Among these, the Harappan civilization was the most expansive, spanning present-day Afghanistan, Pakistan, and North India (*Lal 1997; Possehl 1999; Wright 2010*). However, scholarship on the Harappan civilization has lagged for several reasons. First, colonial-era scholars imposed their ideological frameworks, particularly in the early stages of research, which emphasized indirect interpretations of Harappan antiquities through both historical and contemporary Hinduism. Compounding this issue is the undeciphered Harappan script, which has hindered direct analysis of the civilization's cultural and historical contexts. Secondly, the partition of India and Pakistan in 1947 introduced further challenges. Not only did it divide the subcontinent, but it also fragmented the study of the Harappan civilization into two competing narratives. On one hand, archaeologists in Pakistan have begun classifying the Harappan civilization as a pre-Hindu culture. On the other, Indian scholars increasingly associate it with Hindu or Vedic traditions. This section highlights significant issues—such as nomenclature, religion, and the collapse of the Harappan civilization—demonstrating how these have been profoundly shaped by pseudoarchaeologists and colonial ideologies.

Nomenclature, Colonial ideology and Nationalism:

The term "Harappan civilization" has been profoundly influenced by nationalism, colonial ideology, and pseudo-archaeology. Since its discovery during the British colonial era, imperial ideology played a significant role in shaping its nomenclature and interpretation. Prior to 1925–1926, the civilization was referred to as the *Indo-Sumerian civilization* or a "colony of the Sumerians" due to the resemblance of its artifacts to those of the Sumerian civilization and their geographical proximity. This colonial perspective, reinforced by early surveyors, sought to establish that the civilization originated outside India.

John Marshall (1925–26:75, 1931:91) later coined the term *Indus Civilization*, replacing the *Indo-Sumerian* designation. However, this terminology faced criticism. Mackay (1935–36:39) found the term "Indus Civilization" too restrictive, arguing that the culture extended far beyond the confines of the Indus Valley. He preferred the term *Harappa Culture*, drawing on the archaeological tradition of naming civilizations after their type sites. Piggot (1950:17, 133) also supported this approach. Despite these efforts, Marshall's term *Indus Civilization* gained enduring popularity in the Western world due to the deep historical and geographical associations of the term "Indus." The Indus River was familiar to ancient Greeks (as "Indos") and Romans from the time of Aeschylus, Scylax, Hecataeus, Herodotus, Aristotle, Arrian, Megasthenes, Strabo, Pliny, and Plutarch featuring prominently in Western maps and accounts of the region for centuries (*Chandra 1977; Bury 1958; Milns 1989; Rawlinson 1916; Puri 1939*). During British colonial rule, the Indus River became a central reference point in cartography, trade, and administrative descriptions of South Asia. This entrenched familiarity made "Indus" a logical and intuitive choice for Western archaeologists working within the colonial framework.

Comparison of Preferred Terminology in the Titles of Published Books and Articles Between Indian and Western Authors after Marshall and Wheeler

Fig. 1: Comparison of Preferred Terminology in the Titles of Published Books and Articles Between Indian and Western Authors after Marshall and Wheeler. [Sources: This data collected from www.academia.edu, www.researchgate.net and other various sources, Possehl, 1999, <https://snu-kr.academia.edu/JenniferBates>, <https://independent.academia.edu/AlessandroCeccarelli>, [https://as.nyu.edu/content/dam/nyu-as/anthropology/document /CV%20March%202019%20RWright%201.pdf](https://as.nyu.edu/content/dam/nyu-as/anthropology/document/CV%20March%202019%20RWright%201.pdf), <https://snu-kr.academia.edu/JenniferBates>, <https://york.academia.edu/AdamGreen>, <https://sussex.academia.edu/DanikaParikh>, <https://www.arslibri.com/collections/PossehlLibrary1.pdf>, <https://cambridge.academia.edu/CameronPetrie>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Randall-Law>, <https://wisc.academia.edu/JonathanMarkKenoyer>, <https://www.anthropology.wisc.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/Kenoyer-Full-CV-Sept-132019.pdf>, <https://cambridge.academia.edu/DilipKumarChakrabarti>, <https://asi.academia.edu/RavindraSinghBisht>, <https://independent.academia.edu/shereenratnagar>, Possehl, 1999, https://www.academia.edu/99348779/Annotated_Bibliography_of_Dr_S_P_Gupta_s_Research_Publications, <https://www.cuh.ac.in/admin/uploads/files/shinde.pdf>, <https://independent.academia.edu/KuldeepKumarBhan>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Krishnan-Krishnan>]

Marshall and Mortimer Wheeler had a profound impact on the academic study of the Harappan civilization, shaping the perspectives of scholars in both American and British schools of archaeology. Their contributions earned them titles such as "Great Director General," "Sir" John Marshall, and "Father of Modern Indian Archaeology," "Sir" Mortimer Wheeler (*Possehl 1974, 1979, 1980, 1999; Jarrige 1994; Kenoyer 1983, 1984, 1986, 1991*). Consequently, their followers consistently favored terms like Indus Valley Civilization, Indus Civilization, or Indus Age (*Mackay 1925, 1931; Allchin & Joshi 1970; Possehl 1974, 1979, 1980, 1999; Jarrige 1994; Kenoyer 1983, 1984, 1986, 1991; Parpola 1984, 1986, 1994; Wheeler 1946, 1953, 1960, 1966*).

After 1947, Pakistan opened its archaeological sites to expeditions led by American, British, and French archaeologists. While Pakistani archaeologists predominantly used the term *Harappan Civilization*, Western archaeologists working in Pakistan continued to emphasize the term *Indus Valley Civilization*, reflecting the legacy of colonial nomenclature. Walter A. Fairservis, G. Dales, J. F. Jarrige, G. L. Possehl, M. Kenoyer, R. Meadows, and Rita P. Wright were pivotal figures in advancing the study of the Harappan civilization. Their contributions have been instrumental in shaping contemporary understanding of this ancient culture. However, the ideological frameworks established by John Marshall and Mortimer Wheeler left a lasting imprint on their work. This is evident in their terminology preferences: 77% of the publications by these scholars use the term "Indus Civilization," while only 23% refer to the "Harappan Civilization" (fig. 1). Among them, Possehl and Fairservis demonstrated the most balance, using the term "Harappan Civilization" in 49% and 67% of their works, respectively. In contrast, Kenoyer referenced the Harappan civilization in just 6% of his publications, favoring "Indus Civilization" or "Indus Valley Civilization" in 94% of his writings. Excluding Possehl and Fairservis, the remaining scholars overwhelmingly adhered to colonial terminology, referencing the "Indus Civilization" 81% of the time compared to 19% for the "Harappan Civilization."

This trend continued with their intellectual successors, who still show a strong adherence to neo-colonial ideologies and Eurocentric frameworks. Cameron Petrie (94%) and his associates—Ceccarelli (100%), Bates (94%), Green (86%), and Parikh (85%)—consistently use terms like "Indus Age," "Indus Valley," or "Indus Civilization," even when researching regions such as the Ganga-Yamuna or Ghaggar-Yamuna plains. These choices reflect the persistent influence of colonial ideologies on Harappan studies. The Japanese scholars have also contributed significantly to Harappan research but predominantly adopt the term "Indus Civilization," as demonstrated in the works of Uesugi (2023, 2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018)

and Osada and Uesugi (2008). In contrast, following the lead of A. H. Dani, most Pakistani archaeologists favour the term "Harappan Civilization" in their scholarship.

Since the colonial era, three generations of archaeologists have contributed to advancing Harappan research. Recent efforts include those by newly appointed university faculty and PhD scholars, whose work has significantly shaped understanding of the civilization, particularly in regions like Gujarat and Haryana. Institutions such as MD University in Haryana, MS University in Baroda, Deccan College in Pune, and Kerala University have been at the forefront of this research. However, this paper does not include the work of these contemporary scholars or the so-called "Indian left-wing archaeologists," only a few of whom remain active. Instead, it focuses on the successors of John Marshall, Mortimer Wheeler, B. B. Lal, and S. P. Gupta, whose efforts continue to influence the field.

The terminology used to describe the Harappan civilization in India has evolved through three distinct phases. During the first phase, early archaeologists—including Marshall, Wheeler, and their colleagues and trainees—adopted colonial nomenclature. They referred to the civilization as the "Indo-Sumerian Period" (*Dikshit 1924–25; Sahni 1924–25:74*), "Indus Culture" (*Sahni 1925–26:94*), or "Proto-Indian" (*Hunter 1929, 1932, 1934; Vats 1934–35:38*). This terminology persisted until the mid-20th century and is reflected in terms like "Indus Civilization" (*Vats 1940; Dikshit 1935*), "Indus Valley Civilization" (*Ghosh 1964, 1965*), and "Indus Age" (*Lal 1979, 1984, 1992; Sankalia 1962, 1988; Lahiri 2000; Rao 1973*).

The second phase began in the 1960s, marked by a shift in terminology influenced by American archaeologists like Fairservis (*1961a, 1961b*). During this period, Indian scholars increasingly favored the term "Harappan Civilization," which appeared in 72% of works compared to 18% for "Indus Civilization" and "Indus Age" (*Gupta 1968, 1973, 1974, 1976, 1978, 1982, 1984; Ratnagar 1981, 1986, 2001, 2003; Bisht 1984, 1999, 2000, 2006; Lal et al. 2002*). This phase reflects a growing recognition of the Harappan civilization as distinct from colonial constructs.

The 1990s marked the rise of the BJP and RSS, alongside the emergence of right-wing scholarship spearheaded by B. B. Lal and S. P. Gupta. During this period, the term *Indus-Sarasvati Civilization* gained traction, appearing in 10% of scholarly works (*Gupta 1993, 1996, 1997, 1998; Dikshit 2010, 2012; Dikshit & Mani 2012; Sharma & Sharma 2006; Rao 2014; Chakrabarti 2014; Mani 2017*) (fig. 2). The first and second phases of this scholarship were primarily focused on the *Hindutva*-driven reinterpretation—or *Hindunization*—of the Harappan civilization. In contrast, the third phase sought to

redefine the Harappan civilization as the *Rigvedic Age*, aligning it with narratives rooted in Vedic traditions.

Comparison of Preferred Terminology in the Titles of Published Books and Articles Between Indian Authors after Marshal and Wheeler

Fig.2: Comparison of Preferred Terminology in the Titles of Published Books and Articles Between Indian Authors after Marshal and Wheeler (Source: This data collected from

www.academia.edu, www.researchgate.net and other various sources,

<https://asi.academia.edu/RavindraSinghBisht>, <https://independent.academia.edu/shereenratnagar>, Possehl, 1999, https://www.academia.edu/99348779/Annotated_Bibliography_of_Dr_S_P_Gupta_s_Research_Publications, <https://www.cuh.ac.in/admin/uploads/files/shinde.pdf>, <https://independent.academia.edu/KuldeepKumarBhan>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Krishnan-Krishnan>)

The most significant impediment to Harappan archaeology lies in its persistent entanglement with state-sponsored agendas, spanning British colonial rule, post-independence India, and Pakistan. Mortimer Wheeler exemplifies the archetype of a state-backed archaeologist whose work was deeply embedded in the political ideologies of his era. Wheeler portrayed himself as a lone beacon of knowledge and enlightenment, as he boldly declared in his writings (*Wheeler 1955:220*), yet his research was explicitly tailored to serve the interests of his colonial benefactors.

When appointed to India by the British government in 1944, Wheeler actively sought to frame Harappan archaeology within the colonial narratives of oriental despotism and racial conflict, crafting a narrative

of the civilization's rise and fall that aligned with imperial ideologies (*Kumar 2020:6*). Later, as the Director of Archaeology in Pakistan, he reinforced this ideological alignment through his work, culminating in the publication of *Five Thousand Years of Pakistan: An Archaeological Outline* (1950). In this work, Wheeler deliberately repositioned Harappan archaeology to fit the nascent state's nationalistic framework, further entrenching the discipline in political propaganda.

The Authors of Harappan Civilization: Colonial Narratives and Nationalist Claims:

The hypothesis surrounding the origins of the Harappan civilization has been profoundly shaped first by colonial ideologies and later by *Hindutva* narratives, mirroring the evolution of its nomenclature. Following the civilization's discovery, British colonial archaeologists and their contemporaries largely supported the idea that it originated from the West (*Childe 1926:33; Marshall 1925–26:107; Wheeler 1953:15*). This perspective dominated until Fairservis (*1967:21–24, 41*) challenged the "Mesopotamian idea" of Harappan urbanism, based on his excavations at Kot Diji (*1955–56*) and Amri (*1959–62*).

The publication of *Five Thousand Years of Pakistan: An Archaeological Outline* and the propagation of Aryan invasion theories further fuelled contentious debates between Indian and Pakistani scholars. Both sides sought to substantiate exclusive claims over the Harappan civilization. Wheeler's assertion of Pakistan's antiquity as five thousand years old gained widespread acceptance among Pakistani archaeologists, driven by the belief in the civilization's pre-Vedic, non-Aryan, and non-Hindu character (*Aziz 1965:40–41*).

In response, the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) launched an extensive survey of the Ghaggar-Hakra plain under the leadership of Ghosh (*1953*), leading to the discovery of numerous Harappan sites. Between 1950 and 1990, major sites such as Sothi (*1950–51*), Rupar (*1954–55*), Lothal (*1954–63*), Kalibangan (*1960–69*), Surkotada (*1964–68*), Banawali (*1974–84*), Kuntsi (*1987–90*), and Dholavira (*1989–90*) were unearthed, bolstering India's claims over the Harappan civilization. These discoveries reinforced Fairservis's theory of the indigenous origin of the Harappan civilization, which Indian archaeologists enthusiastically embraced (*Ghosh 1965:113–116; Sharma 1965:132–133*).

Across the border, archaeological missions from Britain, France, and the United States conducted extensive explorations and excavations in Baluchistan, adopting innovative methodologies. These efforts uncovered numerous rural pre-Harappan Chalcolithic cultures in the region, offering new frameworks for understanding the emergence, expansion, and decline of the Harappan civilization. Among these

efforts, two significant archaeological surveys were carried out in Pakistan by Mughal (1977–1978: 84–88).

The first survey, spanning the Indus Valley, identified the Kot Diji culture as an *Early Harappan* phase, suggesting its continuity into the Mature Harappan period. Mughal hypothesized that the epicentre of the Kot Diji culture was situated in the Bahawalpur region, specifically within the central Indus Valley. The second survey, conducted between 1974 and 1977, saw Mughal (1990:11–12; 2000:188–200) extensively investigate the Hakra Valley in the Cholistan region of Pakistan’s Bahawalpur district. This research highlighted the indigenous evolution of the Harappan civilization from earlier cultures in the Indus-Hakra Valley.

Mughal's work in the Hakra Valley represents a pivotal moment in Harappan archaeology, bringing the region into the forefront of archaeological inquiry. His research not only reinforced Ghosh’s theory, which emphasized the indigenous origins and significance of the Ghaggar-Hakra Valley in the Harappan civilization, but also bolstered the claims of right-wing Indian archaeologists who linked the Ghaggar-Hakra to the Rigvedic Sarasvati (Danino 2010; Gupta 2011:157–204; Lal 1998:439–448).

During this period, there was a significant rise in the establishment of right-wing institutions in India, including the *Indian Archaeological Society*, *The History and Culture Society*, *Draupadi Dream Trust*, *Vivekananda International Foundation*, *Dharma Civilization Foundation*, *Akhila Bharatiya Itihas Sankalan Yojana*, and *Infinity Foundation India*—all affiliated with the RSS. Many retired archaeologists from the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) and various universities joined these organizations. Prominent figures such as B.B. Lal, R.S. Gupta, K.N. Dikshit, R.S. Bisht, B.R. Mani, Makhan Lal, V.H. Sonawane, Vasant Shinde, and Dilip K. Chakrabarti, along with retired scientists from institutions like the *Birbal Sahni Institute of Palaeo-sciences*, *Pondicherry University*, *the Indian Meteorological Department*, *the Geological Survey of India*, and *IITs*, have been associated with these RSS-linked entities.

Recognizing the limitations of relying solely on Vedic literature to establish a connection between the Harappan civilization and the *Rigveda*, these right-wing historians and archaeologists have collaborated with scientific institutions, such as the Geological Survey of India and IITs, to validate their claims. The *Geological Survey of India* and *IITs* alone have produced hundreds of articles and research projects on the Sarasvati-Harappa connection. Collectively, these pseudo-archaeologists and scientists seek to push back the dating of the Harappan civilization—from the widely accepted range of 3000 BCE – 2500 BCE

to 7000 BCE – 5000 BCE—using scientific, astronomical, and Vedic literary sources. They argue that the *Vedic* people, inhabiting the Sarasvati Valley, were the true authors of the Harappan civilization (*Lal 2017:12; Dikshit 2017:91; Bhadra 2017:47; Bhatnagar 2017:143*).

Harappan Religion: Interpretations, Misinterpretations, and Ideological Agendas

Similar to nomenclature and theories of origin, interpretations of Harappan religious ideology have been profoundly shaped by the perspectives of Marshall and Wheeler—an influence that persists to this day. Despite extensive efforts to reconstruct Harappan religious practices, archaeologists have yet to identify a single temple at any Harappan site. Instead, much of the scholarship on Harappan religious beliefs has relied on interpretations of so-called religious and ritual objects, such as masks, seals, and terracotta figurines (*Wright 2010*).

Marshall's framework for interpreting Harappan religious ideology was based on two key hypotheses. First, he assumed that the Harappans practiced a centralized *state religion*, akin to those of Mesopotamian and Egyptian civilizations. Second, he employed direct historical analogy, interpreting Harappan religious practices by drawing parallels with both contemporary and historical Indian religions.

To support his theory, Marshall initially sought architectural structures constructed for religious purposes, akin to those found in other ancient civilizations. However, he found no evidence of large temples or monumental statues of deities at Harappa or Mohenjo-Daro. He then turned to his second hypothesis, using comparative analysis to interpret artifacts and religious structures. This approach, while speculative, gained traction and received praise from both his contemporary Hindu archaeologists and later scholars of Hindu religious history. However, it also led to several inaccurate claims, including the identification of a *Mother Goddess cult*, a *fertility cult*, a *Priest-King*, and the *pre-Aryan Pashupati Shiva* tradition.

Marshall asserted that female figurines from Harappan sites represented a *Mother Goddess cult*, drawing a direct comparison to domestic goddess worship in modern Indian households (*Marshall 1931:50*). His hypothesis was heavily influenced by late 19th-century scholarship on popular Indian religion, particularly Monier-Williams's (1887) claim that a localized mother goddess figure protected each community. Based on this assumption, Marshall theorized that the Harappans similarly worshiped a mother goddess. However, later research demonstrated that female terracotta figurines were significantly

less abundant at sites beyond Harappa and Mohenjo-Daro, including Kalibangan, Lothal, Rakhigarhi, and Chanhudaro (*Ratnagar 2016:128*).

Marshall's reliance on Monier-Williams allowed him to circumvent the absence of temple structures in Harappan settlements. However, both he and his successors—Western and Indian alike—failed to consider the archaeological context of the figurines. These objects were not found deliberately buried in ritualistic deposits or submerged in water, as would be expected in a religious setting. Instead, most were recovered from urban waste deposits (*Jansen 2002:219; Ratnagar 2016:128*), making it difficult to substantiate claims of religious significance.

Subsequent scholars have challenged Marshall's interpretations, offering alternative explanations for the figurines. Clark (*2003, 2007*) and Jansen (*1992, 2002*) proposed that Harappan figurines might have represented a wide range of religious and ideological themes, including fertility, shamanic practices, domestic cults, and depictions of life force. Clark (*2007*) specifically noted that neither male nor female figurines exhibit distinct anatomical features indicative of fertility, suggesting instead that they may have conveyed symbolic or shamanic ideas (*Clark 2003*). As new varieties of figurines continue to be discovered, older interpretations are being reassessed, broadening the scope of inquiry into Harappan ritual practices. While the theory of a *Great Mother Goddess cult* has largely been dismissed, the possibility that these figurines played a role in religious or ritual contexts remains open for further examination (*Wright 2010:288*).

Beyond his misinterpretation of terracotta figurines, Marshall employed pseudo-archaeological methodologies, relying on 19th-century and Vedic mythology to support his hypothesis of a *Mother Goddess cult*. His work was deeply influenced by colonial Indologists such as William Jones and Max Müller, leading him to promote a racialized colonial Aryan hypothesis. He claimed that the *Mother Goddess cult* was pre-Aryan (*Marshall 1931:51*), indirectly reinforcing the Aryan invasion/migration theory—an idea that Wheeler would later popularize.

Marshall's portrayal of Harappan figurines as mother goddesses has left a lasting imprint on archaeological discourse (*Ratnagar 2016:113*). His interpretation was widely accepted by both Western (*Dales 1991; Kenoyer 1998; Possehl 2003*) and Indian scholars, many of whom continued to advocate for a *Mother Goddess cult* in Harappan society. In addition to this claim, Marshall (*1931*) linked the civilization to early forms of Shaivism and Shaktism, further reinforcing his comparative approach. He famously identified a seal (*Marshall 1930, Pl. XII, 17*) as depicting *Proto-Shiva*, attributing it with four

iconographical elements: a tricephalic figure, a yogic posture, a trident-like horned headdress, and the presence of four animals. Despite the speculative nature of this interpretation, it was widely accepted by both his contemporaries and later scholars.

Marshall's work has been particularly influential among right-wing historians and archaeologists, who continue to praise his contributions to the study of Harappan religion. His interpretations are cited favourably in *History of Ancient India Vol-II: Protohistoric Foundations*, edited by Dilip K. Chakrabarti and Makhan Lal, a publication associated with the right-wing Vivekananda International Foundation. The editors assert, "*The section on religion by Marshall in Mohenjo-Daro and the Indus Civilization is still the best discussion on the subject.*" (Chakrabarti & Lal 2014:225).

Following Marshall, Wheeler (1966; 1968) also incorporated *Rigvedic*, *Puranic*, and *epic narratives* into his interpretations of Harappan religious ideology, art, and the civilization's decline. Despite the available scientific evidence at the time, Wheeler attributed the collapse of the Harappan civilization to Aryan invasions. He linked the *Rigvedic Pura* with Harappan cities and characterized Indra as *Purandara*, the destroyer of Harappan urban centers (Wheeler 1966:77–83). While his Aryan invasion theory faced criticism from scholars—including right-wing historians—his use of mythology as an interpretative tool was rarely questioned. Instead, Marshall and Wheeler's methodologies laid the groundwork for later right-wing archaeologists to reinterpret Indian history through the lens of mythology, legends, and epics.

B. B. Lal continued Marshall's tradition in interpreting Harappan religious beliefs. Like Marshall, he argued that *Harappan seals and terracotta figurines played a crucial role in understanding Harappan religion* (Lal 1997:223). However, where Marshall's interpretation was limited, Lal and other right-wing archaeologists expanded the religious associations, identifying *Hindu gods, goddesses, and mythological figures* in Harappan artifacts. These included *Sapta Rishi, Sapta Matrikas, Mahisha Mardini, Naga*, and even connections to *Panchatantra* stories (Lal 1997:23–26; Lal 2002).

Marshall's approach—reliant on direct historical analogy—continues to shape right-wing interpretations of Harappan religion. This method has been adopted by contemporary scholars who employ modern and historical religious symbols to analyse Harappan artifacts. For instance, *Brijesh Rawat (2016)*, a Jain and Buddhist art historian and archaeologist, has sought to trace the origins of Jainism to the Harappan civilization. In a discussion regarding his assertion that a particular sculpture from Harappa represents a *Jain Tirthankara-type figure*, Rawat defended his claim by arguing,

"If Marshall and other archaeologists could declare a seal as representing Proto-Shiva based solely on four animals, a trident, and a particular posture, then why can't I do the same? The nude, standing posture is a defining characteristic of Jain sculptures, and there are many examples of similar sculptures and terracotta figures in the Harappan civilization. I am merely applying the same direct historical analogy used by Marshall and archaeologists like B. B. Lal. So, how can I be wrong?" (pers. comm. with Dr. Brijesh Rawat).

Despite the speculative nature of these interpretations, Marshall's framework remains deeply embedded in both Western and Indian scholarship.

Harappan Civilization Reinterpreted: From *Hindunization* to *Aryanization*

After the 1990s, a significant shift occurred in Harappan studies, as right-wing archaeologists and historians redirected their focus from the *Hindunization* to the *Aryanization* of the Harappan civilization. As noted by *Chakrabarti and Lal (2014)* in their discussion of "The Section of Religion" by Marshall, his interpretations were widely accepted, leading to the prevailing notion that the origins of Hinduism can be traced back to the Harappan civilization. The current objective of right-wing scholarship is to establish that the *Rigvedic Aryans* were the true authors of Harappan civilization.

A century of archaeological research has yielded substantial insights into the material culture of the Harappan civilization. However, no definitive scientific evidence has been uncovered regarding the language spoken by its people or the specifics of their religious and social practices. This lack of empirical data has made Harappan archaeology particularly susceptible to appropriation by *Hindutva* narratives (*Chadha 2011:58–59*). Consequently, a new archaeo-ethnic construct—the *Vedic Harappans*—has emerged, integrating literary accounts from *Vedic* texts with the extensive material culture of the Harappan civilization (*Gupta 1995, 1996; Lal 1998, 2002, 2017; Bisht 1999*).

At this stage, right-wing scholarship concentrated on a singular objective: elevating the mythological *Saraswati River* into the realm of archaeology. Prior to 1999, efforts to establish this narrative were primarily undertaken by RSS-affiliated organizations or individual scholars. However, the 1999 general

election, which brought the BJP-led NDA government to power under Prime Minister *Atal Bihari Vajpayee*, provided an unprecedented opportunity for right-wing scholars to advance their agenda.

With strong lobbying from these scholars and the active involvement of the then Minister of Tourism and Culture, *Jagmohan*, the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) launched *The Saraswati Heritage Project* in 2002–03. The initiative sought to legitimize the concept of an *Indus-Saraswati Civilization* and establish the *Rigvedic Aryans* as the creators of the Harappan civilization (*Chadha 2011:74*). As part of the project, ASI initiated excavations at several sites along the dry channel of the *Ghaggar-Hakra River*, including *Chak 86*, *Tarkhanwala Dhera*, *Baror*, *Hansi*, *Bhirana*, and *Juni Kuran*, with the aim of generating scientific data to substantiate these claims.

However, the project was abandoned within a year following the BJP's defeat in the 2004 general election. With the change in government, the responsibility for advancing right-wing narratives in archaeology shifted back to individual scholars and affiliated organizations. By this time, a second generation of right-wing archaeologists had emerged to continue the work pioneered by figures like *S.P. Gupta* and *B.B. Lal*. Among the leading figures vying for influence within RSS-aligned circles were *B.R. Mani*, *K.N. Dikshit*, *Vasant Shinde*, and *D.K. Chakrabarti*, positioning themselves as successors to *Lal* and *Gupta*.

K.N. Dikshit seamlessly assumed leadership of the *Indian Archaeological Society (IAS)* after *S.P. Gupta*, continuing its established ideological trajectory. Following the excavation of *Ayodhya*, *B.R. Mani*—widely regarded as a strong contender to succeed *B.B. Lal* in the *Archaeological Survey of India (ASI)*—lacked significant academic impact but played a pivotal role in the *saffronization* of Indian institutions and universities. Both *Mani* and *Vasant Shinde* have consistently aligned themselves with *Hindutva*-driven narratives, frequently endorsing works that promote a revisionist interpretation of Indian history.

A striking example of this is their praise for *The Saraswati Civilization: A Paradigm Shift in Ancient Indian History (2019)* by *Major General G.D. Bakshi*. The book attempts to establish the *Saraswati River* as the cradle of *Vedic* culture and its connection to the *Indus Valley Civilization*. However, its claims rest on speculative interpretations, selective readings of archaeological and textual evidence, and unscientific citation methods, positioning it within a nationalist framework aimed at glorifying India's ancient past. Labelled as *pseudo-archaeology*, the book dismisses scholarly consensus and evidence-based methodologies in favour of conjecture. Nevertheless, *Shinde* described it as "*pure scientific*

research indicating a truly landmark shift in the history of the country," while Mani lauded its "interdisciplinary approach," emphasizing the need to integrate archaeology with tradition, literature, and science to "uncover historical truths" (see review on Bakshi, 2019).

D.K. Chakrabarti, a Professor Emeritus of South Asian Archaeology at Cambridge University, has positioned himself as both an *anti-colonialist* and a *nationalist archaeologist*. His body of work—including *The Battle for Ancient India: An Essay in the Socio-Politics of Indian Archaeology* (2008), *The Problem of the Sarasvati River* (2009), *Nation First: Essays in the Politics of Ancient Indian Studies* (2014), *Nationalism in the Study of Ancient Indian History* (2021), and *Towards a Nationalist Narrative of India's Ancient Past* (2022)—reflects his ideological stance. He also co-edited the *History of Ancient India* series (2014–2020), an eight-volume work published by the RSS-affiliated *Vivekananda International Foundation*, widely regarded as a *saffronized* reinterpretation of Indian history.

Despite building his career in *European academia*, Chakrabarti now actively promotes a nationalist agenda in Indian archaeology, seemingly disregarding the historical consequences of nationalist archaeology in other contexts. In *19th and 20th-century Germany*, nationalist archaeology became deeply intertwined with ideological constructs that fostered *exclusion, racism, and genocide*. The *Nazi regime* notoriously manipulated archaeology to fabricate a mythical *Aryan identity*, using it to legitimize racial hierarchies and oppressive policies (Arnold, 1990, 1992, 2006). The central aim of nationalist archaeology, historically, has been to shape public opinion through exaggeration and fabrication masquerading as fact (Boese 2002:5).

Chakrabarti established his reputation by critiquing colonial archaeologists and historians, as well as some Indian institutions like Deccan College, Pune, and MS University, Vadodara. However, his criticisms reflect a selective approach. He primarily targets figures such as Sankalia, Wheeler, Rapson, and left-wing Indian historian (Chakrabarti 2022). While India is home to some of the world's most renowned left-wing historians, including D.D. Kosambi, R.S. Sharma, and Romila Thapar, it is well understood that they are historians rather than archaeologists. Their reliance on secondary data for archaeological insights is evident in their writings. As mentioned earlier, Wheeler served as a state-sponsored archaeologist during the colonial period in India and later in Pakistan. Similarly, Chakrabarti has positioned himself in a comparable role in contemporary India. He is a key thinker for the RSS-affiliated organization, *Vivekananda International Foundation*, where he works to steer public opinion toward a nationalist narrative.

Notably, Chakrabarti refrains from critiquing right-wing archaeologists from Deccan College or any western scholar like Marshall, Fairservis, Dales, and many more who fit in their perspectives align with right-wing ideologies. His efforts seem aimed at steering Indian archaeology toward a specific ethno-nationalist framework, aligning with the RSS's ideological goals. In his recent book, Chakrabarti explicitly advocates for "a new nationalist archaeological agenda and narrative" (2022:39), which is aligning closely with the ideological framework of the BJP-RSS. Furthermore, Chakrabarti attempts to align Modi and the RSS's ideology of "one nation, one culture, one people" with the Harappan civilization. By disregarding the regional traits of the Harappan civilization, Chakrabarti asserts that "it has been necessary to emphasize, repeatedly, the point that the Indus civilization is the fountainhead of the whole length of the indigenous civilizational tradition of India, which has continued down to the modern period because of its integrity" (Chakrabarti 2022:119).

In doing so, he continues to criticize archaeologists from Deccan College, Pune, and MS University, Vadodara, for shedding new light on the regional variations within the Harappan civilization in Gujarat and Haryana region (Chakrabarti 2017:228, 2022:119). This criticism reflects his broader effort to project a monolithic narrative onto India's ancient past, sidelining diversity in favour of a unified, ethno-nationalist interpretation.

Similarly, *Chakrabarti's* (2008, 2009, 2010, 2014, 2020, 2021, 2022) work advances the notion of an uninterrupted and *indigenous* Indian civilization while rejecting external influences such as *Aryan migration*. He has championed the *Sarasvati River* as a central feature of Indian history, equating it with the mythical *Rigvedic Sarasvati* and aligning the *Harappan civilization* with *Vedic culture*. This approach prioritizes *cultural nationalism* over *scientific rigor*, reinforcing a *Hindutva-centric* historical framework that marginalizes the diverse historical contributions of other communities and cultures.

Chakrabarti's prolific writings and alignment with right-wing narratives culminated in his being awarded the *Padma Shri* in 2019 by the BJP government, underscoring his role in reshaping Indian archaeological and historical discourse within a *nationalist* framework. The only significant limitation in his academic career remains his *lack of field archaeology experience*.

Vasant Shinde, former *Professor* and *Vice-Chancellor* of the *Deccan College Post-Graduate and Research Institute* in Pune, and founder of the *Society of South Asian Archaeology (SOSAA)*, is a prominent figure in right-wing archaeology. Following the failure of the *Saraswati Heritage Project* in 2004, Shinde launched a new exploration and excavation initiative in the *Ghaggar Basin* in 2007, in

collaboration with the *Research Institute for Humanity and Nature, Kyoto, Japan*. The project aimed to investigate the Harappan culture in the region using interdisciplinary approaches, including archaeology, geology, climatology, and environmental studies. However, Shinde's underlying objective was to examine the role of the *Saraswati River* in the Harappan civilization. As he stated,

"One of the aims of the Ghaggar Project is to study the history of the Ghaggar River and its impact on the early cultures that flourished there. Efforts will be made to study its active and passive phases too" (Shinde et al. 2008:79).

During 2006–2007, the project included explorations along the *Ghaggar River* in *Haryana* and *Rajasthan*, along with excavations at sites such as *Girawad, Farmana, and Mitathal*. The excavation at *Farmana* was particularly significant, as it marked Shinde's first attempt to extract DNA from mature Harappan burials. However, this effort failed due to severe contamination resulting from poor retrieval methods and the degraded condition of the samples (Chadha 2011:50).

Shinde later undertook excavations at *Rakhigarhi* with similar objectives, collaborating with *Seoul National University* (Shinde et al. 2018). After screening over 61 skeletal samples, the project achieved a groundbreaking result: for the first time in Harappan archaeology, genetic data was successfully extracted from a single individual—a woman identified as 16113 (Shinde et al. 2019). The genetic data formed the basis for two scientific articles, published simultaneously in *September 2019* in *Science* (Narasimhan et al. 2019) and *Cell* (Shinde et al. 2019).

Shortly after the publication of these articles, Shinde and geneticist *Niraj Rai* (Shinde and Rai 2019) held a press conference to present the Harappan DNA findings to the Indian public. However, this event bore hallmarks of pseudo-archaeology, as it emphasized nationalist interpretations rather than strictly scientific conclusions. Although the peer-reviewed articles in *Science* and *Cell* refrained from making unsubstantiated claims, the press conference was laden with ideological assertions. It promoted the absence of Aryan invasion or migration, identified the Harappan civilization as *Vedic*, associated the *Saraswati River* with *Rigvedic* texts, and endorsed the *Out of India* theory.

The rhetoric used in the press conference reinforced *Hindutva* narratives through the deliberate use of *saffronized* terminology, emphasizing concepts such as *Aryans, havan kund, horses, and the Saraswati River*. This conflation of scientific research with cultural and political ideologies drew significant criticism for distorting archaeological discourse. While the published articles themselves maintained

academic rigor, the press conference exemplified the strategic use of pseudo-archaeology, prioritizing ideological interpretations over evidence-based scholarship. This dual approach raised serious concerns about the politicization of archaeology and the ethical responsibilities of researchers in shaping public perceptions of history, making it one of the most prominent cases of pseudo-archaeology in contemporary India.

Following the widely publicized press conference, *Prof. Vasant Shinde* gained substantial media recognition, earning the pseudonym “*Rakhigarhi Man*” in Indian television, print, and social media. He was subsequently invited to deliver a series of *Zoom* lectures and participate in interviews across various organizations and news channels. Through these appearances, he effectively brought the *Harappan–Rigvedic* discourse into the mainstream, particularly through television—a platform frequently criticized for promoting pseudo-archaeology.

As *Brian Fagan* (2003:49) argues, television prioritizes storytelling and audience engagement over academic accuracy or the dissemination of reliable information. Pseudo-archaeological programs, with their sensationalist narratives, often attract more public interest than rigorous scientific discourse. *Shinde’s* media strategy epitomized this phenomenon, leveraging public fascination to amplify a controversial reinterpretation of history. His approach blurred the distinction between scholarly inquiry and ideological storytelling, illustrating how pseudo-archaeology can be used as a powerful tool to reshape historical narratives in service of political and cultural agendas.

Concluding Remarks:

Pseudo-archaeology in India has undergone a transformation from a colonial construct into a powerful tool for advancing political and cultural agendas. The media-centric approach, conspiratorial narratives, misuse of science in archaeology, and mythology as artifacts are main characteristics of Indian pseudoarchaeology. Miss interpretation of mythology can be traced to colonial-era practices, where myths and speculative interpretations often overshadowed scientific rigor. The trajectory of these distortions—from colonial speculation to nationalist propaganda—demonstrates how archaeology can be weaponized to serve ideological objectives rather than scientific inquiry.

The roots of this distortion can be traced to *British colonial archaeology*, where figures like *John Marshall* and *Mortimer Wheeler* introduced speculative interpretations that merged mythology with history. *Marshall’s* identification of *Shaivism* and *Shaktism* in Harappan religious iconography,

alongside *Wheeler's* racialized theory implicating *Indra* in the civilization's collapse (*Wheeler 1947:82*), set a precedent for pseudo-archaeological narratives. These interpretations, though framed as academic inquiry, were steeped in orientalist and Eurocentric assumptions that undermined the scientific foundations of Indian archaeology.

Post-independence, rather than being critically dismantled, these colonial frameworks were repurposed by nationalist ideologues. Right-wing scholarship, particularly within the *Hindutva* movement, sought to establish the Harappan Civilization as the *cradle of Vedic culture*, rejecting earlier colonial narratives while paradoxically adopting the same methodological flaws—reliance on historical analogies, selective use of evidence, and an ideological reading of the past. This was exemplified by the concerted effort to reframe the Harappan Civilization within an indigenous Aryan framework, extending its chronology from 2500 BCE to as early as 7000 BCE (*Dikshit and Mani 2012*), reinforcing a narrative of deep historical continuity between *Harappan* and *Vedic* traditions.

The *Saraswati Heritage Project (2002–03)* epitomized this nationalist reinterpretation, aiming to legitimize the *Indus-Saraswati Civilization* and establish the *Rigvedic Aryans* as its creators. However, its abrupt termination following the 2004 electoral defeat of the *BJP* did little to curb the ideological momentum that had been generated. By this time, a new generation of right-wing archaeologists, including *B.R. Mani*, *K.N. Dikshit*, *Vasant Shinde*, and *D.K. Chakrabarti*, had stepped in to carry forward the legacy of *S.P. Gupta* and *B.B. Lal*, further entrenching pseudo-archaeological narratives within academic and institutional frameworks.

The rise of digital platforms has profoundly accelerated the spread of pseudo-archaeology in India. With the advent of *social media*, *YouTube*, *digital conferences*, and *online publications*, nationalist interpretations of history have found an expansive audience beyond academic circles. During the *COVID-19 pandemic*, platforms such as *IIT Gandhinagar*, *Vivekananda International Foundation*, *Centre for Indic Studies*, *Argumentative Indians*, *Infinity Foundation Official* and *the Print*, played a significant role in amplifying *Hindutva*-driven narratives. These platforms, often unmoderated and lacking academic scrutiny, have enabled the unchecked dissemination of revisionist claims, further embedding nationalist interpretations within public consciousness.

Pseudo-archaeology thrives on its ability to simplify complex historical narratives into easily digestible and emotionally resonant claims. Unlike rigorous archaeological research, which acknowledges uncertainties and contradictions, pseudo-archaeology presents history in absolutes, reinforcing

preconceived notions of cultural and national superiority. The narrative of *Vedic Harappans*, for example, merges literary accounts from *Vedic texts* with archaeological data to construct a seamless, unbroken historical continuum, despite the absence of definitive linguistic or material evidence to support such a claim (*Gupta 1995, 1996; Lal 1998, 2002, 2017; Bisht 1999*).

The consequences of pseudo-archaeology extend far beyond academic discourse. At its mildest, it fosters a nationalistic pride that distorts historical understanding; at its most extreme, it serves as a justification for exclusionary ideologies, rewriting the past to reinforce contemporary political agendas. The *Ayodhya conflict* of the 1990s serves as a stark reminder of how the manipulation of historical narratives can translate into real-world violence. As *Colley (1995)* noted, ‘*Ayodhya* exemplifies the perilous intersection of archaeology and nationalist ideology, where alternative historical narratives fueled religious and political tensions rather than fostering intellectual debate’.

The resurgence of such pseudo-historical narratives in recent years reflects a broader global trend in which archaeology is increasingly politicized to serve nationalist and ideological goals. From *Turkey’s* reimagining of its *Ottoman past* to *China’s* strategic use of archaeology in territorial disputes, the instrumentalization of history is not unique to India. However, the distinct challenge in the Indian context lies in the scale and institutionalization of this process. With government-backed projects, academic endorsements, and digital proliferation, pseudo-archaeology in India is no longer confined to fringe groups—it is embedded within mainstream discourse.

The challenge ahead is to reclaim archaeology as a discipline grounded in scientific inquiry rather than ideological assertion. The continued advancement of genetic, linguistic, and material analyses offers a counterbalance to pseudo-historical claims. However, the effectiveness of such efforts depends not only on the academic community but also on public engagement with rigorous, evidence-based historical research.

The responsibility of archaeologists, historians, and educators is greater than ever. Countering pseudo-archaeology requires a commitment to methodological rigor, critical analysis, and public outreach. It necessitates challenging oversimplified nationalist claims with nuanced scholarly perspectives and fostering an environment where history is explored as a complex and dynamic process rather than a tool for political validation.

In conclusion, the trajectory of pseudo-archaeology in India—from colonial speculation to nationalist propaganda—underscores the dangers of distorting the past to serve contemporary ideologies. As *Wheeler (1947:82)* famously remarked, "*On circumstantial evidence, Indra stands accused.*" While the culpability of Indra remains debatable, but in my opinion "*Wheeler and Marshall undoubtedly stand accused of the development of pseudo-archaeology in India*". Their methodologies, though framed as scientific, set a precedent for historical distortions that have been appropriated and amplified by nationalist ideologues. As India navigates the complexities of its past, the challenge remains to uphold historical inquiry as a pursuit of truth rather than an instrument of ideological imposition.

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